

MODERN APPROACHES AND INNOVATIONS IN IMPROVING LANGUAGE SKILLS

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Abstract

This course work “Modern approaches and innovations in improving language skills” explains impact of technologies on pupils not only for primary school but also for upper classes. It shows explains the usage of different approaches in teaching English to make pupils interested in learning a foreign language.

Key words: technologies, available, in classrooms all over the world, illustrated, embedded.

What innovations in English language teaching (ELT) have had the biggest impact on your teaching?

English language teaching is evolving all the time, particularly alongside advances in technology. But what changes have had the biggest impact on teachers in recent years? Here are what appear to be the top ten innovations for teachers, in no particular order.

1. Digital platforms

When we discuss innovation, we often immediately think of the internet and what we can now do online. Facebook and especially Edmodo, which creates a safe online environment for teachers, students and parents to connect, are popular with teachers.

Cloud-based tools like GoogleDocs have also become indispensable. For teacher Tyson Seburn, it's 'where I've moved so much of individual and (because of its functionality) collaborative writing with students...'

The list of digital platforms is extensive and growing all the time. A multimedia manual like Digital Video by Nik Peachey (nominated for an ELTons award for innovations in teacher resources) can help teachers navigate the complicated, and sometimes overwhelming, world of digital resources, enabling teachers to create activities, lessons and courses from a range of digital tools.

2. Online corpora

The use of corpora – large text collections used for studying linguistic structures, frequencies, etc. – used to be the privilege of lexicographers. But with most corpora now available online, and quite a few for free, teachers now have access to information about the way language is used in authentic texts and speech.

Teachers no longer have to panic when students ask them about the difference between 'trouble' and 'problem'. And it's not just teachers who benefit. To find out if more people say 'sleepwalked' or 'sleptwalk' (for example), students can simply search the words on Google, which uses the internet as its corpus.

3. Online CPD (continuous professional development) and the global staffroom
The advent of the internet and the growth of social media have certainly allowed teachers of English from all over the world to form online communities that act like a huge global staffroom. Twitter and ELT blogging, for example, have 'opened up a network of people who can offer advice, support and ideas', says Sandy Millin. Participants who are generous with their time, ideas, and contacts find they receive much in return.

4. Mobile learning and BYOD (bring your own device)

The development of mobile technology and the proliferation of smart phones have enabled many of us to access the internet and a huge variety of apps on the go. Learners benefit too, from apps like WIBBU, and podcasts like Luke's English Podcast – Learn British English with Luke Thompson – nominated for an ELTons award in the category of digital innovation.

Teachers are also able to build on their teaching knowledge and skills by listening to podcasts like The TEFL Commute or join 50,000 teachers from more than 200 countries and watch webinars or archived videos of talks by TEFL teachers on EFL Talks. Both are nominated for an ELTons for innovation in teacher resources.

And if teachers and students are gaining so much from their mobile devices, why ban them from classrooms? It seems that getting students to bring their own devices to class is fast becoming a game-changer in ELT practice.

For teacher Ceri Jones, tools like WhatsApp and Padlet help build channels of communication beyond the classroom. She says: 'I often don't have the hardware or the connectivity in teen classes to use internet, so students using their own devices is great – and it means they have a record of the resources we've used to check back on after class...'

5. Communicating with people online

The ability to communicate online with people outside the classroom via Skype and similar tools has enabled students to meet and interact with others in English. In monolingual classes (i.e., most English classrooms around the world), this could give much-needed motivation to students who otherwise might not have the opportunity to interact with anyone in English.

And as for teachers, the ability to converse with students face-to-face online has opened up a whole new market for Skype lessons and online classes.

6. Online authentic materials

One of the biggest benefits of the internet for language learners is the sudden widespread availability of authentic resources. As David Deubelbeiss points out, this enables teachers to use 'content with messages students want to hear'. We can now access the daily news, watch trending videos on YouTube, read the latest tips on TripAdvisor... the possibilities are endless.

But with so much content available to us, choosing the right online materials is crucial for efficient and effective learning. Keynote by National Geographic Learning, makes use of TED talks to develop a pedagogically sound approach to language learning, while Language Learning with Digital Video (Cambridge University Press) looks at how teachers can use online documentaries and YouTube videos to create effective lessons. Both resources are nominated for this year's ELTons awards.

7. The IWB (interactive white board)

The IWB started appearing in classrooms in the early parts of this century and has now become a staple of many classrooms in Britain and around the world. It allows us to save and print notes written on the board, control the classroom computer from the whiteboard, play listening activities on the sound system, use the screen as a slide for presentations, access the internet, and so on. The possibilities seem endless.

But the addition of an IWB to a classroom does not automatically make for a better learning experience. Indeed, unless teachers use them skilfully to complement teaching and learning, they are little more than a distraction.

As teacher David Dodgson explains, some people 'love the shiny stuff', believing that simply standing in front of an IWB is effective integration of education technology. It's not.

8. Dogme (or materials-light teaching)

For teachers like Matthew Noble, discovering the Dogme approach to language teaching was 'galvanising'. A communicative approach that eschews published textbooks in favour of conversational communication between learners and teacher, Dogme signals a departure from a one-size-fits-all approach to classroom materials.

For many teachers, this 'unplugged' approach represents a new way of looking at the lesson content, and the chance to break free from self-contained language points and give more time to student-generated language.

9. Students steering their own learning

Over the last couple of decades, learning has gradually been moving from a teacher-centred top-down approach to a student-centred, bottom-up one. The trend has accelerated rapidly in recent years with the growing quantity and quality of information on the internet. In many respects, this has changed the teacher's role from that of knowledge-transmitter to consultant, guide, coach, and/or facilitator.

One example is the 'negotiated syllabus', previously the domain of the business English teacher, who would conduct a needs analysis before tailoring a course to suit the participants. But we've come to recognise that there is nothing general about the general English learner either, and increasingly, teachers involve students in decisions about what to do in the classroom.

The ELTons-nominated *Connections E-textbook* (a project by Zayed University in the UAE) takes this a step further and involves the students in the design of their e-textbook, allowing them to make decisions on page layout and the clarity of task instructions.

Different approaches and strategies for the development of listening skill. Students listen to the text and, based on their vocabulary and grammar knowledge, process and analyze one after the other, sounds, words, phrases, sentences and the entire text during the decoding process, to grasp the meaning of the text. In order to be successful in the bottom-up approach, students need to know words and grammar of the language. Such are most of the practices in schools nowadays, including the activities such as: dictation, listening, identification, repetition, questions and answers after the exercise, etc. Usually such exercises are aimed at finding the structure of a sentence, tense, place, positive or negative forms, key words carrying meaning, types of words, order of actions in a sentence, etc. Such an approach is supported by the majority of the textbooks in use and favored by teachers because it does not require much involvement besides following the exercises in the textbook. The questions put forth are mainly factual and do not require much elaboration, concentration and attention by teachers. For example, the sentence Students have been waiting for their teacher is accompanied by questions such as: what verb tense is it? What type of sentence is it? Is the action complete or incomplete? What is the subject? And so on. On the other hand, "the top-down approach refers to the context and the use of prior knowledge to grasp the meaning of a message. While the bottom-up approach moves from language to meaning, the top-down approach starts from meaning to achieve language. The knowledge sought could be

information, situational or contextual knowledge and schemes, different paradigms and general relations students have about the topic". For example, students listen to the sentence: "National elections were held yesterday in Albania". The key word is elections. Based on the broader context, prior knowledge, and established schemes regarding the elections in Albania, students can react with questions: Who won? Were the elections fair? Did many people go to the polls? Is this good or not for Albania? For the European integration process? What about Kosovo? Which politicians won? What is the importance of democratic elections? Such questions and follow up discussions build up the context for subsequent exercises on this topic. The top-down approach starts from the scheme and general knowledge to elicit the meaning of the text and to develop the language skills of students.

Through this approach, the teacher helps students to:

- Use key words to create the scheme of the listening discourse (text) Elicit the context of the text Identify and understand the role and the aims of participants
- Identify the causes and effects of actions I
- identify unstated details in the text Foresee and formulate questions regarding the text.
- In top - down activities students develop skills in order to: Think and formulate a set of questions regarding the text (and then listen whether those questions have been addressed)
- To compile a list of things they know about a topic and a list of new things they would like to learn (and then listen to find out and compare their expectations) Read the words of one speaker and anticipate the answer of the other speaker (then listen to find out the answer)
- Read few issues, points, highlights which are to be mentioned in a text, then listen for verification Read a part of a story, anticipate how it will continue or end and then listen for verification
- Read news headlines, anticipate the news content, and then listen for verification. In general, the top-down approach encourages the use of resource material resulting in authentic learning, while the bottom-up approach starts from language material by imposing an analytical and descriptive approach.

Experienced teachers, with proper professional capital, to use Hargreaves and Fullan's terminology, will combine both approaches, based on the needs of students. Assessing the needs and wishes of students can be done during the

planning or the implementation of a class hour (always taking into account the characteristics of students) and with active participation of students. In this way, the autonomy and the responsibility of students will increase regarding their own success and the class hour. In order to illustrate the approaches discussed above, we have made an adjustment by combining the stages of listening activities in class by Field and the Richards concept of top-down and bottom-up approaches through the elaboration of the topic of national elections. The following table presents different aspects of these two approaches and their possible application in a lesson.

Teaching soft skills and critical thinking skills

As English cements its position as the world's lingua franca, many of our students are now learning English to oil the wheels of communication in the worlds of business, trade, education, and tourism. To enable our students to become better communicators, we should perhaps go beyond grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation, and look at helping them communicate effectively in international settings.

Learner resources nominated for an ELTons award this year include Richmond Business Theories (Richmond ELT), which features online resources that help teachers and students with soft skills like problem-solving, presentation skills, time management and decision-making. Academic Presenting and Presentations (Levrai and Bolster) looks specifically at the communication skills needed when making a presentation at college or university.

Another ELTons nominee is The Thinking Train (Helbling Languages), which believes in starting young. It helps children develop critical thinking skills that could support them not just in their English learning but in the learning of other subjects and life skills.

And perhaps it is this ability to think and reflect that will enable us as teachers and learners to take any innovation out there and make it work in our context for our students. After all, as a wise teacher of mine used to say, 'It's never the tool, but the user that makes the difference.'

In this early part of the 21st century the range of technologies available for use in language learning and teaching has become very diverse and the ways that they are being used in classrooms all over the world, as illustrated in this book, have become central to language practice. We are now firmly embedded in a time when digital technologies, the focus of this book, are what Bax has referred to as 'normalised' (2003, 2011) in daily life in many parts of the world, although not amongst all people as there are digital divisions everywhere (Warschauer,

2003), and still not always in the world of education. However, digital tools, or what I will describe in Chapter 7 as ‘technical cultural artefacts’ have long been a feature of the world of education (Bates, 2005), and particularly language education (Salaberry, 2001). These digital tools are, of course, central in what I would argue is the established and recognised field of computer assisted language learning (CALL), but are also increasingly a core part of English language teaching (ELT) in general.

People continue to debate the use of the term CALL itself, asking whether it is still relevant. Levy and Hubbard making the argument for (2005), whilst Dudeney and Hockly (2012) are rather less convinced. In a world where we increasingly see laptops, tablet computers, or mobile phones as the technology of choice, it might be argued that we are at a tipping point when this common term will soon disappear.

It can be seen from the case studies and illustrative examples in this chapter that technology has a significant role to play in enhancing the delivery of English language teaching and learning in the primary sector. The range of technologies now available can support teachers in a variety of ways both inside the young learner classroom, but also increasingly in the home environment and while learners are on the move about their daily lives. Technological use is clearly ‘situated’, dependent on context and predicated on the notion that what works in one context may not be entirely replicable in another. However, creative practitioners will always be able to see the potential for an idea and are particularly adept at customising approaches to meet the individual needs of their learners. With the continuing reduction in manufacturing costs, greater coverage and increasing speeds of communication networks and the development of a ‘read/write Web’, English language teachers have an unparalleled opportunity to ensure their curricula and teaching styles genuinely meet the needs of their 21st century learners.

The internet can be a vast treasure trove of English learning games and activities,

but teachers should not underestimate the potential for making their own games for their learners. Indeed, there is also huge potential to enable learners to become ‘game-developers’ and publish for their peers. Language games and activities not only provide a framework for reviewing existing language but can also be used to explore and acquire new language. There are numerous online

tools for developing games and activities as well as standalone packages such as '2Simple's 2Do It Yourself' (<https://www.2simple.com/2diy/>) software, which is easy enough for younger learners to use as well as providing enough complexity to keep older learners engaged. Here is a useful blog posting about creating language learning games

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